

PHOTOGRAPHIC SENSITISERS. PART I. MEROCARBOCYANINES

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The preparation of five merocarbocyanine dyes derived from 4-phenyl-, 4-*p*-methoxyphenyl-, 4-*p*-ethoxyphenyl-, 4-*p*-bromophenyl-2-methylthiazoles and 2-methylbenzothiazole has been described. Their acetanilidovinyl intermediates were first prepared and then condensed with 3-ethyl-rhodanine to furnish the desired merocyanines,

Recently many dyes are being used in photography for modifying the spectral sensitivity of silver halide emulsions. The region of sensitivity conferred by the dye molecules is not confined to the visible spectrum, but extends to infra-red and even to longer wave-lengths. Because of the wide limits of sensitivity, thus provided, sensitising dyes have become indispensable in modern photography.

The dyes, which show the photographic sensitising action most powerfully, generally belong to the group known as the polymethine dyes which may be divided into three main divisions: the cyanines (I), *p*-dialkylaminostyryl dyes (II) and the merocyanines (III).

In the cyanine dyes, two basic nuclei are linked together, the two nitrogen atoms being separated by a conjugated chain of carbon atoms. In *p*-dialkylaminostyryl dyes, the conjugated chain exists, but one of the nitrogen atoms forms part of a

dialkylaminostyryl groups. These are much less important than cyanines. The third group of dyes, a more recent development, known as merocyanines, are as significant as cyanines. "Meros" means a portion. These are called merocyanines, since a part of the molecule resembles cyanines. The second half of the molecule is derived from an acidic rather than a basic nucleus. Unlike the other two classes, these dyes are unionised.

Whereas the cyanines are characterised by an amidinium ion resonance (IV), the merocyanine contains the amidic resonance system as shown in the simple forms in (V) or in a typical merocyanine dye (VI).

(IV)

(V)

(VIa)

(VIb)

5-[{3-Methyl-2-(3H)-4-p-bromophenylthiazolylidene}-ethylidene]-3-ethyl-2-thiothiazolid-4-one.—The above methiodide (5.41 g.) and 3-ethyl-rhodanine were refluxed in acetic anhydride in presence of fused sodium acetate for 2 hours. The product after being cooled was washed several times with cold water, followed by acetone, to remove any tarry residue. Pure material was obtained by three recrystallisations from acetic acid in reddish brown plates, m.p. 218-20° (decomp.), yield 48%. (Found: C, 46.39; H, 3.37. $C_{17}H_{18}ON_2BrS_3$ requires C, 46.46; H, 3.41%).

4-p-Ethoxyphenyl-2-methylthiazole was prepared by the same method as described in the preceding thiazole by taking *p*-ethoxyphenacyl bromide, m.p. 58°, yield 65%. (Found: C, 65.63; H, 5.82. $C_{13}H_{13}ONS$ requires C, 65.77; H, 5.93%).

4-p-Ethoxyphenyl-2-methylthiazole Methiodide.—4-p-Ethoxyphenyl-2-methylthiazole (2.19 g.) and methyl iodide (1.42 g.) were heated in a sealed tube for 30 hours. The product was washed with cold water, treated with ether and recrystallised from hot methanol, m.p. 204°, yield 60%. (Found: C, 43.10; H, 4.32. $C_{13}H_{13}ONIS$ requires C, 43.21; H, 4.43%).

2-(2-Acetanilidovinyl)-4-p-ethoxyphenylthiazole methiodide was prepared in a similar way as the 4-p-bromophenyl analogue from 4-p-ethoxyphenyl-2-methylthiazole methiodide (3.61 g.) and diphenylformamidine (1.96 g.) and purified similarly. Pure material was obtained by two recrystallisations from acetic acid, m.p. 188° (decomp.), yield 48%. (Found: C, 52.05; H, 4.41. $C_{22}H_{22}O_2N_2IS$ requires C, 52.17; H, 4.54%).

5-[{3-Methyl-2-(3H)-4-p-ethoxyphenylthiazolylidene}-ethylidene]-3-ethyl-2-thiothiazolid-4-one.—A mixture of the preceding methiodide (5.06 g.) and 3-ethyl-rhodanine (1.61 g.) was refluxed in acetic anhydride in presence of fused sodium acetate for 3 hours. After cooling, the product was stirred and washed with cold water, followed by acetone. Pure material was obtained by three recrystallisations from acetic acid from which it separated in deep reddish violet needles, m.p. 167° (decomp.), yield 42%. (Found: C, 56.30; H, 4.87. $C_{19}H_{20}O_2N_2S_3$ requires C, 56.43; H, 4.95%).

2-Methylbenzothiazole methiodide was prepared in the same manner as described in the preceding methiodides and crystallised from hot water, m.p. 217° (*Chem. Abst.*, 1925, 19, 2339). Doja and Banerjee (this *Journal*, 1946, 23, 223) report m.p. 219°. The product was obtained in 75% yield (Doja and Banerjee have not recorded the yield of the compound). (Found: C, 37.04; H, 3.36. Calc. for $C_9H_{10}NIS$: C, 37.12; H, 3.42%).

2-(2-Acetanilidovinyl)-benzothiazole Methiodide.—The preceding methiodide (2.9 g.) and diphenylformamidine (1.96 g.) in acetic anhydride were heated under reflux for 70 minutes. The product obtained after removing excess of the solvent was treated with ether and washed by acetone. The acetone-washed product was pure enough to be used for further reaction. Pure material was obtained by two recrystallisations from methanol, m.p. 178° (decomp.), yield 58%. (Found: C, 49.43; H, 3.75. $C_{18}H_{17}ON_2IS$ requires C, 49.55; H, 3.89%).

5-[{3-Methyl-2-(3H)-benzothiazolylidene}-ethylidene]-3-ethyl-2-thiothiazolid-4-one was prepared by refluxing the above methiodide (4.36 g.) and 3-ethyl-rhodanine in acetic anhydride in presence of fused sodium acetate for 3 hours. The product,

after being stirred and washed with cold water, was washed with acetone to remove tarry products. Pure material was obtained by three recrystallisations from acetic acid from which it separated as dark red crystals, m.p. 148-49° (decomp.), yield 50%. (Found: C, 53.82; H, 4.10. $C_{18}H_{14}ON_2S_2$ requires C, 53.89; H, 4.19%).

4-Phenyl-2-methylthiazole and its methiodide, and 4-*p*-methoxyphenylthiazole and its methiodide have been prepared and their m.p., yield and analytical data have been reported elsewhere.

2-(2-Acetanilidovinyl)-4-phenylthiazole methiodide was prepared by refluxing 4-phenyl-2-methylthiazole methiodide (3.17 g., 1M) and diphenylformamidine (1.96 g., 1M) in acetic anhydride (10-15 c.c.) for about an hour. Excess of acetic anhydride was removed by distillation under reduced pressure and the dark residue was treated with ether. The gummy product after being washed with water was solidified by keeping it in contact with methanol and was treated with acetone to remove tarry products. The product was finally recrystallised from hot methanol, m.p. 162-63° (decomp.), yield 55%. (Found: C, 51.89; H, 4.04. $C_{20}H_{18}ON_2IS$ requires C, 51.95; H, 4.10%).

5-[3-Methyl-2 (3H)-4-phenylthiazolylidene]-ethylidene]-3-ethyl-2-thiothiazolid-4-one.—The above methiodide (4.62 g., 1M) and 3-ethyl-rhodanine (1.61 g., 1M) were refluxed in acetic anhydride in presence of fused sodium acetate as the condensing agent for 2 hours. After cooling, the material was washed several times with cold water, followed by acetone to remove any tarry residue and was finally recrystallised from hot methanol. Pure material was obtained by two recrystallisations from hot methanol as shining reddish plates, m.p. 176-77° (decomp.), yield 45%. (Found: C, 56.48; H, 4.33. $C_{17}H_{16}ON_2S_3$ requires C, 56.66; H, 4.44%).

2-(2-Acetanilidovinyl)-4-*p*-methoxyphenylthiazole methiodide was prepared by refluxing 4-*p*-methoxyphenyl-2-methylthiazole methiodide (3.47 g., 1M) and diphenylformamidine (1.96 g., 1M) in the same way as the corresponding benzothiazole methiodide. Pure material was obtained by two recrystallisations from hot methanol, m.p. 178° (decomp.), yield 52%. (Found: C, 51.04; H, 4.13. $C_{21}H_{21}O_2N_2IS$ requires C, 51.22; H, 4.26%).

5-[3-Methyl-2 (3H)-4-*p*-methoxyphenylthiazolylidene]-ethylidene]-3-ethyl-2-thiothiazolid-4-one was prepared as usual from the preceding thiazole methiodide (4.92 g., 1M) and 3-ethyl-rhodanine (1.61 g., 1M) and purified as described before. Pure material was obtained by two recrystallisations from acetic acid in lustrous reddish brown needles, m.p. 173° (decomp.), yield 40%. (Found: C, 55.24; H, 4.48. $C_{18}H_{18}O_2N_2S_3$ requires C, 55.39; H, 4.61%).

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